

CASE REPORT

Post-Varicella Guillain Barre Syndrome: A Case Report

Pranshi Agarwal*, Grijesh Kumar Singh**, Akhil Sai Kumar*, Utkarsh Bansal**

*MD (Pediatrics), Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India, *email: pranshi.agar@gmail.com*, **MD (Pediatrics, Associate Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India, *email: rathoriaekansh@yahoo.com*, •Postgraduate, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India *email: akhilsai5dachepalli@gmail.com*, **MD (Pediatrics), Professor and Head, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India, *email: utkarsh1003@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Guillain Barre Syndrome (GBS) is an acute immune-mediated polyneuropathy. An antecedent infection is reported in more than half of the patients one to two weeks ahead of the outset of weakness. Here we present a case of nine-year old boy who presented with GBS after Varicella Zoster Virus (VZV) infection which is rarely being reported in children.

INTRODUCTION

Guillain-Barré syndrome (GBS) is an acute onset immune-mediated disorder of the peripheral nervous system that destroys nerves in the peripheral nervous system causing weakness, usually symmetrical, progressing to paralysis. Many distinct pathogens have been identified as triggers of this acute polyneuritis. It has been reported that upto 70% of patients have a history of apreceding illness 1 to 6 weeks before the onset of GBS. The most prevalent are gastrointestinal or respiratory illnesses. [1]

The disease is self-limited, with muscle strength usually reaching a nadir within 2 to 3 weeks, followed by partial or complete recovery taking place over weeks to months. Up to 20% of patients may require ventilatory support. [2,3,4]

A multitude of case reports and studies have incriminated a myriad of different infections and other events as probable precedents of GBS. Reports of GBS associated with Varicella-Zoster Virus (VZV) are rare, with only a few cases being reported in children.

Also, in previous reports, GBS following varicella was reported to be of a milder course with complete clinical recovery. This is in contrast to our case where the patient had a fulminant course with respiratory muscle involvement along with delayed and slow recovery.

CASE REPORT

A nine-year old previously healthy boy presented to pediatric emergency with complains of breathlessness and difficulty in swallowing for last 1 day. On taking further history parents informed that he had inability to walk for eight days, which began with weakness in lower limbs which progressed by complete inability to walk. This was followed two days later by the inability to sit and hold objects. After a day he developed a change in voice, difficulty in swallowing, and difficulty in breathing, when he was brought to our hospital.

He was treated locally for his weakness but his condition didn't improve. There was no history of trauma, headache, vomiting, seizures, throat pain, swelling over neck or ear discharge.

Past history suggested that two weeks prior to the event, the patient had a history of varicella infection. There was no history of diarrhea nor any preceding history of vaccination.

At the time of admission, he was afebrile and hemodynamically stable. His respiratory rate was 25/min with shallow pattern of respiration and oxygen saturation of > 94% on 2L/min O₂ via nasal prongs. His single breath count was 4.

On initial neurological examination, he was found to be well oriented to time, place, and person. Pupils were normal in size and reactive to light. His gag reflex was absent and he had a nasal twang of voice indicating bulbar involvement. The other cranial nerves were intact. His extremities were hypotonic with diminished reflexes. Power was 3/5 in upper extremities and 2/5 in lower extremities. Sensation in limbs was intact. Rest general and systemic examination was within normal limits.

Considering the ascending progression of his weakness with bulbar palsy, a diagnosis of GBS seemed highly likely.

Complete blood count, liver function test, kidney function tests, and serum electrolytes revealed no significant abnormality. Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) studies were done which revealed no cells or microorganisms, the protein was elevated (120 mg/dL), and sugar was normal (60mg/dL). CSF culture was sterile. His nerve conduction studies showed acute motor axonal neuropathy variant of GBS.

The patient was managed in the pediatric intensive care unit with strict monitoring of vitals. Intravenous Immunoglobulin (IVIG) was given @ 0.4 mg/kg for 5 days. Thereafter, his respiratory muscle weakness began to improve. RT feeds were given and physiotherapy was started. During the course of the hospital stay his blood pressure and heart rate remained normal ruling out autonomic involvement. During 10 days of inpatient period, his muscle weakness and dysphagia, improved gradually. The patient was discharged with residual lower limb weakness with advice to continue physiotherapy. Fortunately, patient recovered well without any sequel after two months of follow up.

DISCUSSION

GBS is immune-mediated post-infectious polyneuropathy, involving chiefly motor but also sensory and sometimes autonomic nerves. An antecedent infection is described in more than half of the patients often 10-14 days ahead of the outset of weakness. Frequently reported infections and events are *Campylobacter jejuni*, Cytomegalovirus, Epstein-Barr virus, *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, rabies vaccine, and "swine flu" vaccine. [5,6]

GBS subtypes & variants:

- Acute inflammatory Demyelinating Polyneuropathy (AIDP)
- Acute motor axonal neuropathy (AMAN)
- Acute motor & sensory axonal neuropathy (AMSAN)
- Miller Fischer syndrome (MFS)

The term GBS is often used interchangeably with AIDP, but the motor axonal form is increasingly being recognized as another predominant subtype. In a North Indian study conducted by Aneja et al, AMAN was the predominant electrophysiological subtype, accounting for 69.4% of patients. [7] In various studies from India [8,9], China [10], and Japan [11] axonal variants are reported to be the common subtype. AIDP has been observed to be more common in developed countries [12-16]. The rationale for such a distribution remains obscure. [17]. AIDP & AMAN are discriminated by results of nerve conduction studies and an associated pattern of anti-ganglioside antibodies.

A fulminant and less prevalent type of GBS, AMSAN carries a grave prognosis for recovery.

Miller Fischer variant (MFS), an uncommon GBS variant is characterized by the triad of ophthalmoplegia, ataxia, and areflexia.

CLINICAL FEATURES

The patient with GBS present with weakness of the lower extremities ascending proximally and thereafter involve muscles of the arm, face, and oropharynx, and in worst cases, respiratory muscles. Frequently, subtle sensory manifestations like transitory dysesthesias and muscle tenderness precede the outset of weakness. The weakness is usually symmetrical qualitatively, if not quantitatively. Weakness progresses expeditiously, and closely 50% of patients reach maximal weakness by 2 weeks, and 80% by 3 weeks, and remaining by 4 weeks. [18] Hyporeflexia or areflexia are the consistent characteristic of GBS but may not be present in the initial course of the disease. [19]

Cranial neuropathies occur in 45-75% of cases in different case series. Facial paresis is found in at least half of the patients. [19] Bulbar involvement occurs in 50% of cases and can result in respiratory insufficiency. [20] Severe bulbar and respiratory muscle involvement may lead to death if GBS is not recognized and treated timely.

Sensory involvement, though less common, is frequently limited to loss of vibration sense.

Autonomic dysfunction of various degrees has been reported. Lability of blood pressure and heart rate, episodes of profound bradycardia or tachycardia, and occasional asystole occur warranting close cardiac monitoring in such patients. Urinary retention may occur in up to one-third of patients. [21-23] It is likely secondary to sacral parasympathetic nerve and pudendal motor nerve dysfunction. [22-24]

Gastrointestinal motility disorders occur in 15% of severely affected GBS patients. [23]

DIAGNOSTIC STUDIES

Cerebro-spinal fluid (CSF) examination and Nerve Conduction Velocity (NCV) are important ancillary studies for confirming the diagnosis of GBS. The CSF protein is usually elevated to more than twice the upper limit of normal and there is no pleocytosis (cytoalbuminologic dissociation). Cytoalbuminologic dissociation in a patient with acute polyneuropathy is essentially diagnostic of GBS. Notably, these findings may not be apparent in the first week after the onset of symptoms.

NCV and electromyography (EMG) are sensitive to early signs of peripheral nerve inflammation. Motor and sensory nerve conduction velocities are reduced to a variable extent. EMG shows acute denervation of muscle.

Serological tests give helpful support for the early diagnosis of GBS and its variants. However, the value of specific serological tests is confined to MFS and AMAN variants only as in AIDP specific ganglioside antibody are not detected.

Elevated GM₁, GM_{1B}, GD_{1a} ganglioside antibodies are found in the AMAN variant and anti-GQ_{1b} ganglioside antibodies are consistently found in 95- 98% of patients with MFS. [19,20]

Imaging studies, more specifically MRI of the brain and spine, are most useful to exclude brainstem or spinal cord disease as a cause of weakness.

TREATMENT

Patients with milder weakness and slow progression may be treated expectantly, with observation for stabilization and spontaneous remission.

Severe or rapidly progressive muscle weakness is treated with immunotherapy.

Definitive:

Intravenous Immunoglobulin (IVIG) and Plasma exchange (PE) are effectual immunotherapies for patients with GBS if administered during the initial few weeks of the illness. [25-39]

Common protocols include IVIG in the dose of 0.4 g/kg/day for 5 consecutive days or 1 g/kg/day for 2 days. [20]

PE is another equally effective treatment modality. It is recommended to exchange 50 mL/kg plasma volume, five times over 10-14 days. [25,27,30,31] There is no advantage of using both together. [40]

There is no compelling evidence favoring one treatment over the other. [29]

Corticosteroids are not indicated as both prednisolone and pulse dose methylprednisolone, have not proven to be advantageous in a few randomized controlled trials. [41]

The prevention of the most dreaded complications of GBS, respiratory failure, and autonomic dysfunction, leads to a greater likelihood of the positive outcomes. [42] Therefore vigilant monitoring of respiratory and bulbar function, heart rate, and blood pressure are of utmost importance, especially during evolving phase.

Supportive:

- Upto 30% of patients with GBS may develop respiratory failure necessitating mechanical ventilation. Rapidly evolving disease (onset to admission <7 days), the severity of limb weakness and occurrence of facial and bulbar weakness are prognosticators of the need for mechanical ventilation. [43]
- Neuropathic pain should be treated aggressively with narcotic analgesics where necessary and with medications such as gabapentin.
 - Gabapentin is given in the dose of 5 mg/kg/dose at bedtime, followed by 5mg/kg/dose BD on day 2. The dose is escalated to 5 mg/kg/dose three times a day on day 3. (maximum 300mg/dose). Then the dose is titrated to effect. Usual dose range is 8-35 mg/kg/day. [44]
 - Acetaminophen or non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents can be tried as primary therapy for pain but are often less effective. [45]
- Chest physiotherapy and frequent oral suctioning aid in preventing atelectasis in patients with impaired cough.
- Skilled nursing care is essential with proper bed positioning and continuous change in posture.
- Prevention and prompt treatment of nosocomial infections are the important part of care.
- Enteral feedings should be initiated early to prevent muscle wasting and facilitate weaning.
- Physiotherapy is started early as it helps prevent contractures, joint immobilization and venous stasis.

COURSE AND PROGNOSIS

Approximately 15% of GBS patients have a mild condition, remain ambulatory and recover after a few weeks. Conversely, 5-20% have a fulminant course and develop flaccid quadriplegia and ventilator dependence often within 2 days of onset of symptoms. [19]

Although most patients recover functionally, 20% still have residual motor weakness one year later.

Clinical features predicting the severe course and slow recovery include cranial nerve involvement, need for ventilatory support, and maximum disability at time of the presentation. The children with demyelinating forms of GBS generally recover more quickly than those with axonal forms. [20]

Improvement usually follows a gradient opposite the direction of involvement, with bulbar function recovering first and lower extremity weakness resolving last.

Up to 5% of patients may have a recurrence after recovery and are generally responsive to immunomodulatory treatment. [19,20]

CONCLUSION

- Guillain-Barre' syndrome (GBS) is a heterogeneous disease characterized by symmetrical limb weakness progressing in ascending fashion with hyporeflexia or areflexia, sensory disturbances, and cranial nerve deficits in some patients.
- The diagnosis relies on the clinical impression obtained from the history and examination, although cerebrospinal fluid analysis and nerve conduction studies usually provide evidence supportive of the diagnosis.
- The clinician must also be familiar with mimics and variants to promptly and efficiently reach an accurate diagnosis.
- IVIG and plasmapheresis are effective treatment modalities. Diligent supportive care is essential to minimize the risk of mortality.

DECLARATIONS

Ethical approval: Approval taken by the Institute Ethics Committee.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:

Dr Utkarsh Bansal

Professor & Head, Department of Pediatrics,
Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki,
Uttar Pradesh, India
email : utkarsh1003@gmail.com

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